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The more experience you gain, the more you should be able to simplify your thoughts or ideas. We should be ready to answer feedback questions and teach with a level of simplicity of the more experiences we exclaim to have. If not, then what good are those experiences?

People believe they have lived longer, similar to gaining more experiences. You might be right about aging, not concerning gaining more experience unless you can fulfill this instance. For example, you cannot say you are a chief, but when presented with the necessities, you don't know how and where to begin. That also goes for every discipline.

We should be careful about exclaiming that we have gained more experience because we have lived longer. Expressing we are someone when we are not. It is not a problem to say I don't know or to say I am still learning when we have not developed that skill and have solved a problem with it for the benefit of others. Moreover capable of teaching it to others in a way they would understand to apply them during applications.

We are novice seekers and understand how it felt when we couldn't understand a discourse without the help of someone who has what we have been seeking. We become overwhelmed when we meet someone who can solve our problems effectively and efficiently. However, not for our benefit but also to use that knowledge and solve problems more competently and to teach others in a way they would be able to accomplish a purpose; functioning effectively.

I am aware that everybody may not agree with my perspective. My sincere desire is not an imposition on others but instead to stimulate a conversion that eventually leads to better development practices in discipline contexts. My prayers as I share my thoughts; now will provide insights and perhaps be a blessing to you.

“Live for yourself and you will live in vain; live for others, and you will live again.” Bob Marley